

IMPROVEMENT OF MONETARY CREDIT POLICY IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: By improving the monetary and credit policy in Uzbekistan, we will ensure economic growth, full employment and stability of the balance of payments. That is, in the case of full employment, we reduce or eliminate the effect of inflation on the production of the gross national product.

Key words: monetary policy, Central Bank, mandatory reserve ratio, interest rate, inflation, employment and full employment, money supply.

Introduction: The monetary and credit policy is determined by the state and implemented by the Central Bank. With its help, any state implements the task of ensuring economic stability in the country. The ultimate goals of implementing the monetary and credit policy are economic growth, full employment, prices and is to ensure the stability of the balance of payments. In order to achieve these goals, it is necessary to maintain the optimal levels of the national currency in circulation, the interest rate, and the national currency exchange rate.

Main part: To fulfill the tasks mentioned above, the Central Bank uses a number of tasks.

Three main instruments of monetary policy are distinguished:

1. Account rate.
2. Mandatory reserves norm
3. Open market operations.

With the help of them, the Central Bank affects the money supply or interest rate in the form of money or mainly bank deposits, changes its supply and thereby regulates money-credit circulation.

One of the tools of monetary and credit policy is the method of changing the mandatory bank reserve ratio. Mandatory bank reserves are the amount of bank deposits that are not used for credit purposes. Reserves perform two main functions: they create conditions for current regulation of bank liquidity and limit credit issuance. The Central Bank sets the minimum rate of reserves that commercial banks are obliged to keep in the Central Bank, and with the help of this tool, they affect their ability to lend. The higher this rate, the less excess

reserves and the lower the ability of commercial banks to “create money” through lending. Otherwise, this ability will be high.

For example, if this rate is 25%, then 200 soums out of 800 soums deposited in the bank is a mandatory bank rate. In this case, the bank will be able to lend only 600 soums. Now let’s assume that the rate is reduced to 10%, then the bank will be able to lend 720 soums and increase the initial money supply to 720 soums.

Mandatory reserve norm of the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan

(from August 5, 2021)

Obligation type	Mandatory reserve regulations
1	2
Deposits of legal entities in national currency*	4%
Deposits of legal entities in foreign currency	18%
Deposits of individuals in national currency*	4%
Foreign individuals deposits in foreign currency	18%

* An averaging coefficient (0.8) is applied to these types of obligations

.Such a decrease leads to an increase in the amount of the money multiplier and, of course, to an increase in the money supply in the economy. The increase in excess reserves of commercial banks increases their asset operations, and this has a positive effect on the development of the real sector of the economy. Does not need to be used separately. On the contrary, several tools are often used at once, that is, complex policy implementation often occurs in practice.

So what are the implications for monetary policy? The monetary policy implemented by the government has a direct impact on the level of GDP, employment and prices. Suppose that output in the economy is falling and unemployment is rising. In such conditions, the state tries to increase the money supply through the Central Bank using the tools we discussed above. As a result, the money supply will increase, and the interest rate will decrease. This increases the demand for investments and, in turn, leads to an increase in the amount of GDP. In this way, the state will achieve its goal in a certain period of time, the backwardness of production will stop, the number of unemployed will decrease, and the income of the society will increase.

When talking about the consequences of monetary policy, it is necessary to distinguish between short-term and long-term consequences of this policy. If in the short term the increase in the state money supply stimulated the growth of the GDP and achieved a certain level of efficiency, in the long term the effectiveness of these measures may decrease.

Conclusion: Based on the information given above about “Monetary policy”, we can conclude that “Monetary policy” solves the problems of the state, economic growth, the living standards of the population, and solves the problems encountered in the country’s economy. And we can safely say that it is an economic way that can help to improve them.

List of used literature:

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